

CONSTRUCTING INFINITE FAMILIES OF GENERALIZED PYTHAGOREAN TRIPLES

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Abstract: In this article, we show how to construct an infinite family of generalized Pythagorean triples. Then, we consider how Fermat's Last Theorem relates to this construction.

Keywords: Pythagorean triple, primitive Pythagorean triple, convergent infinite geometric series, Fermat's Last Theorem.

1. INTRODUCTION

If a , b , and c are positive integers, then (a, b, c) is called a Pythagorean triple [2] if $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$. The integers within a Pythagorean triple are usually arranged in increasing order. Some well-known Pythagorean triples are $(3, 4, 5)$, $(8, 15, 17)$, and $(10, 24, 26)$. (a, b, c) is called primitive if $\text{gcf}(a, b, c) = 1$. Note that $(3, 4, 5)$ and $(8, 15, 17)$ are primitive, while $(10, 24, 26)$ is not. We can generalize the concept of a Pythagorean triple as follows. If $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c, n$, and k are positive integers, and $k \geq 3$, then we shall call $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ a generalized Pythagorean triple, or an n^{th} degree k -tuple, if $a_1^n + a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n = c^n$. We shall arrange the integers within an n^{th} degree k -tuple in non-decreasing order and shall say that $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ is primitive if $\text{gcf}(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c) = 1$. For example, $(3, 4, 5, 6)$ is a primitive 3^{rd} degree 4-tuple because $3^3 + 4^3 + 5^3 = 6^3$ and $\text{gcf}(3, 4, 5, 6) = 1$. Recall that an infinite geometric series [1] of the form $1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots$ converges to $\frac{1}{1-x}$ provided that $|x| < 1$. Fermat's Last Theorem [2], which was proven by English mathematician Andrew Wiles in 1995, states that there exist positive integers a, b, c , and n that satisfy the equation $a^n + b^n = c^n$ if and only if $n = 1$ or 2 . In this article, we show how to construct an infinite family of generalized Pythagorean triples from a given n^{th} degree k -tuple. Then, we discuss some consequences of Fermat's Last Theorem that are related to this construction.

2. CONSTRUCTING AN INFINITE FAMILY OF GENERALIZED PYTHAGOREAN TRIPLES

Proposition 1: Given an n^{th} degree k -tuple $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ with $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 3$, we can construct an n^{th} degree $(k + i(k - 2))$ -tuple for each $i = 1, 2, \dots$

Proof: If $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ is an n^{th} degree k -tuple with $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 3$, then $a_1^n + a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n = c^n$. Now, select any one of the integers a_1, a_2, \dots , or a_{k-1} (say, a_1) and form the convergent infinite geometric series whose first term is 1 and whose common ratio is $\left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n$. Then, we have $1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{3n} + \dots = \frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n} = \frac{1}{\frac{c^n - a_1^n}{c^n}} = \frac{c^n}{c^n - a_1^n}$. That is, $\frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n} = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} \left[1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} + \dots \right] = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} \cdot \frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n}$. Multiplying each side of the equation

$\frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n} = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \frac{a_1^{2n}}{c^n(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n)}$ by $c^n(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n)$ gives us $c^{2n} = c^n(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n) + a_1^n(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n) + a_1^{2n}$. Therefore, $c^{2n} = (a_2c)^n + \dots + (a_{k-1}c)^n + (a_1a_2)^n + \dots + (a_1a_{k-1})^n + a_1^{2n}$, or equivalently, $(c^2)^n = (a_2c)^n + \dots + (a_{k-1}c)^n + (a_1a_2)^n + \dots + (a_1a_{k-1})^n + (a_1^2)^n$. Hence,

$(a_1^2, a_1a_2, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}, a_2c, \dots, a_{k-1}c, c^2)$ is an n^{th} degree $(k + (k - 2))$ -tuple. Also, $\frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n} = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n +$

$\left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{3n} \left[1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \dots\right] = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{3n} \cdot \frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n} = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} +$

$\frac{a_1^{3n}}{c^{2n}(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n)}$. Multiplying each side of the equation $\frac{c^n}{a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n} = 1 + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a_1}{c}\right)^{2n} + \frac{a_1^{3n}}{c^{2n}(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n)}$ by

$c^{2n}(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n)$, we obtain $c^{3n} = c^{2n}(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n) + a_1^n c^n(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n) + a_1^{2n}(a_2^n + \dots + a_{k-1}^n) + a_1^{3n}$, so $c^{3n} = (a_2c^2)^n + \dots + (a_{k-1}c^2)^n + (a_1a_2c)^n + \dots + (a_1a_{k-1}c)^n + (a_1^2a_2)^n + \dots +$

$(a_1^2a_{k-1})^n + a_1^{3n}$, or equivalently, $(c^3)^n = (a_2c^2)^n + \dots + (a_{k-1}c^2)^n + (a_1a_2c)^n + \dots + (a_1a_{k-1}c)^n + (a_1^2a_2)^n + \dots + (a_1^2a_{k-1})^n + (a_1^3)^n$. This means that $(a_1^3, a_1^2a_2, \dots, a_1^2a_{k-1}, a_1a_2c, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}c, a_2c^2, \dots, a_{k-1}c^2, c^3)$ is an

n^{th} degree $(k + 2(k - 2))$ -tuple. Observe that the given n^{th} degree k -tuple $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ may or may not be primitive. If $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ is primitive, then the n^{th} degree $(k + (k - 2))$ -tuple

$(a_1^2, a_1a_2, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}, a_2c, \dots, a_{k-1}c, c^2)$ is primitive and the n^{th} degree $(k + 2(k - 2))$ -tuple $(a_1^3, a_1^2a_2, \dots, a_1^2a_{k-1}, a_1a_2c, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}c, a_2c^2, \dots, a_{k-1}c^2, c^3)$ is primitive if and only if $\text{gcf}(a_1, c) = 1$. Also, the

integers in $(a_1^2, a_1a_2, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}, a_2c, \dots, a_{k-1}c, c^2)$ are all different, and the integers in $(a_1^3, a_1^2a_2, \dots, a_1^2a_{k-1}, a_1a_2c, \dots, a_1a_{k-1}c, a_2c^2, \dots, a_{k-1}c^2, c^3)$ are all different, if and only if the integers in

$(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ are all different. By iterating this procedure, we can construct an n^{th} degree $(k + i(k - 2))$ -tuple for each $i = 1, 2, \dots$.

The following numerical example illustrates how to construct a 3rd degree 6-tuple and a 3rd degree 8-tuple from a given 3rd degree 4-tuple.

Example 1: Let $a_1 = 3, a_2 = 4, a_3 = 5$, and $c = 6$. Then, $(3, 4, 5, 6)$ is a 3rd degree 4-tuple because $3^3 + 4^3 + 5^3 = 6^3$. Now, select any one of the integers 3, 4, or 5 (say, 3) and form the convergent infinite geometric series whose first term is 1 and whose common ratio is $\left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3$. Then, $1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^9 + \dots = \frac{1}{1 - \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3} = \frac{1}{\frac{6^3 - 3^3}{6^3}} = \frac{1}{\frac{4^3 + 5^3}{6^3}} = \frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3}$.

That is, $\frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 \left[1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 + \dots\right] = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 \cdot \frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \frac{3^6}{6^3(4^3 + 5^3)}$.

Multiplying each side of the equation $\frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \frac{3^6}{6^3(4^3 + 5^3)}$ by $6^3(4^3 + 5^3)$ gives us $6^6 = 6^3(4^3 + 5^3) + 3^3(4^3 + 5^3) + 3^6$, from which it follows that $6^6 = 24^3 + 30^3 + 12^3 + 15^3 + 3^6$, or equivalently, $36^3 = 24^3 + 30^3 +$

$12^3 + 15^3 + 9^3$. Therefore, $(9, 12, 15, 24, 30, 36)$ is a 3rd degree 6-tuple. Also, $\frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 +$

$\left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^9 \left[1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \dots\right] = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^9 \cdot \frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 + \frac{3^9}{6^6(4^3 + 5^3)}$. Multiplying each side of

the equation $\frac{6^3}{4^3 + 5^3} = 1 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^3 + \left(\frac{3}{6}\right)^6 + \frac{3^9}{6^6(4^3 + 5^3)}$ by $6^6(4^3 + 5^3)$ yields $6^9 = 6^6(4^3 + 5^3) + 3^36^3(4^3 + 5^3) +$

$3^6(4^3 + 5^3) + 3^9$, from which we get $6^9 = 6^64^3 + 6^65^3 + 3^34^36^3 + 3^35^36^3 + 3^64^3 + 3^65^3 + 3^9$, or equivalently, $216^3 = 144^3 + 180^3 + 72^3 + 90^3 + 36^3 + 45^3 + 27^3$. This means that $(27, 36, 45, 72, 90, 144, 180, 216)$ is a

3rd degree 8-tuple. Observe that the 3rd degree 4-tuple $(3, 4, 5, 6)$ is primitive, but the 3rd degree 6-tuple $(9, 12, 15, 24, 30, 36)$ and the 3rd degree 8-tuple $(27, 36, 45, 72, 90, 144, 180, 216)$ are not primitive because $\text{gcf}(3, 6) >$

1. Also, the integers in $(9, 12, 15, 24, 30, 36)$ are all different, and the integers in $(27, 36, 45, 72, 90, 144, 180, 216)$ are all different, because the integers in $(3, 4, 5, 6)$ are all different.

3. SOME NOTEWORTHY CONSEQUENCES OF FERMAT'S LAST THEOREM

Corollary 1: Let n be a positive integer. Then, there exists an n^{th} degree k -tuple $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, c)$ for each $k = 3, 4, \dots$ if and only if n equals 1 or 2.

Proof: Fermat's Last Theorem tells us that n^{th} degree 3-tuples exist if and only if $n = 1$ or 2 . By Proposition 1, we know that, given an n^{th} degree 3-tuple, we can construct an n^{th} degree $(3 + i(3 - 2))$ -tuple for each $i = 1, 2, \dots$

Example 2: Let a, b, c , and n be positive integers that satisfy the equation $a^n + b^n = c^n$. Then, by Fermat's Last Theorem, (a, b, c) is an n^{th} degree 3-tuple, where $n = 1$ or 2 . Now, select either one of the integers a or b (say, a) and form the convergent infinite geometric series whose first term is 1 and whose common ratio is $(\frac{a}{c})^n$. Then, $1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} + (\frac{a}{c})^{3n} + \dots = \frac{1}{1 - (\frac{a}{c})^n} = \frac{1}{\frac{c^n - a^n}{c^n}} = \frac{c^n}{c^n - a^n} = \frac{c^n}{b^n} = (\frac{c}{b})^n$. Since $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} [1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} + \dots]$, we have $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{c^2})^n \cdot (\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{bc})^n$. Multiplying each side of the equation $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{bc})^n$ by $(bc)^n$, we find that $(c^2)^n = (bc)^n + (ab)^n + (a^2)^n$. Thus, (a^2, ab, bc, c^2) is an n^{th} degree 4-tuple. Also, since $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} + (\frac{a}{c})^{3n} [1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + \dots]$, we have $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{c^2})^n + (\frac{a^3}{c^3})^n \cdot (\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{bc^2})^n + (\frac{a^3}{bc^2})^n$. Multiplying each side of the equation $(\frac{c}{b})^n = 1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a^2}{bc^2})^n + (\frac{a^3}{bc^2})^n$ by $(bc^2)^n$, we obtain $(c^3)^n = (bc^2)^n + (abc)^n + (a^2b)^n + (a^3)^n$. This means that $(a^3, a^2b, abc, bc^2, c^3)$ is an n^{th} degree 5-tuple.

Now, if we substitute the values $a = 3, b = 4$, and $c = 5$ into (a, b, c) , (a^2, ab, bc, c^2) , and $(a^3, a^2b, abc, bc^2, c^3)$, respectively, we obtain the following 2^{nd} degree k -tuples for $k = 3, 4$, and 5 : $(3, 4, 5)$, $(9, 12, 20, 25)$, and $(27, 36, 60, 100, 125)$. Note that since $(3, 4, 5)$ is primitive and $\text{gcf}(3, 5) = 1$, $(9, 12, 20, 25)$ and $(27, 36, 60, 100, 125)$ are both primitive. Also, the integers in $(9, 12, 20, 25)$ are all different, and the integers in $(27, 36, 60, 100, 125)$ are all different, because the integers in $(3, 4, 5)$ are all different.

Consider the following two observations about certain infinite geometric series.

Proposition 2: Let a, c , and n be positive integers with $a < c$. Then, the sum, S , of the convergent infinite geometric series $1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} + (\frac{a}{c})^{3n} + \dots$, each of whose terms can be expressed as the n^{th} power of a rational number, is equal the n^{th} power of a rational number, $(\frac{c}{b})^n$, if and only if there exists a positive integer b such that $a^n + b^n = c^n$.

Proof: Since a and c are positive integers and $a < c$, the sum, S , of this infinite geometric series is $\frac{1}{1 - (\frac{a}{c})^n} = \frac{1}{\frac{c^n - a^n}{c^n}} = \frac{c^n}{c^n - a^n}$, which equals the n^{th} power of a rational number if and only if $c^n - a^n = b^n$ for some positive integer b . By Fermat's Last Theorem, such a positive integer b exists if and only if $n = 1$ or 2 .

Corollary 2: Suppose a, b, c , and n are positive integers that satisfy the equation $a^n + b^n = c^n$. Let S be the sum of the series $1 + (\frac{a}{c})^n + (\frac{a}{c})^{2n} + (\frac{a}{c})^{3n} + \dots$, and let S' be the sum of the series $1 + (\frac{b}{c})^n + (\frac{b}{c})^{2n} + (\frac{b}{c})^{3n} + \dots$. Then, $S + S' = S \cdot S' = (\frac{c^2}{ab})^n$ if and only if n equals 1 or 2.

Proof: Since $S = (\frac{c}{b})^n$ and $S' = (\frac{c}{a})^n$, we have $S + S' = \frac{c^n}{b^n} + \frac{c^n}{a^n} = \frac{c^n(a^n + b^n)}{a^n b^n} = \frac{c^{2n}}{a^n b^n}$ and $S \cdot S' = \frac{c^n}{b^n} \cdot \frac{c^n}{a^n} = \frac{c^{2n}}{a^n b^n}$. Therefore, $S + S' = S \cdot S' = (\frac{c^2}{ab})^n$. By Fermat's Last Theorem, this occurs if and only if n equals 1 or 2.

4. EXTENDING THE CONSTRUCTION TO SUMS AND DIFFERENCES

We conclude this article by demonstrating how to construct equations that express the n^{th} power of a positive integer as an alternating sum of n^{th} powers of positive integers for n equals 1 or 2. This construction can be extended, by a technique similar to that displayed in the proof of Proposition 1, to express the n^{th} power of a positive integer in terms of more general sums and differences of n^{th} powers of positive integers for any positive integer n .

Example 3: Let a, b, c , and n be positive integers, with $a < b$, that satisfy the equation $a^n + b^n = c^n$. Then, by Fermat's Last Theorem, (a, b, c) is an n^{th} degree 3-tuple with $n = 1$ or 2 . Now, form the convergent infinite geometric series whose first term is 1 and whose common ratio is $-\left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n$. Then, $1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{2n} - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{3n} + \dots = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n} = \frac{1}{\frac{b^n + a^n}{b^n}} = \frac{1}{\frac{c^n}{b^n}} = \left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n$. Since $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{2n} \left[1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{2n} - \dots\right]$, we have $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{b^2}\right)^n \cdot \left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{bc}\right)^n$. Multiplying each side of the equation $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{bc}\right)^n$ by $(bc)^n$, we see that $(b^2)^n = (bc)^n - (ac)^n + (a^2)^n$. Also, since $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{2n} - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{3n} \left[1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \dots\right]$, we have $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{b^2}\right)^n - \left(\frac{a^3}{b^3}\right)^n \cdot \left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{b^2}\right)^n - \left(\frac{a^3}{b^2c}\right)^n$. Multiplying each side of the equation $\left(\frac{b}{c}\right)^n = 1 - \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^n + \left(\frac{a^2}{b^2}\right)^n - \left(\frac{a^3}{b^2c}\right)^n$ by $(b^2c)^n$ yields $(b^3)^n = (b^2c)^n - (abc)^n + (a^2c)^n - (a^3)^n$.

Substituting the values $a = 3, b = 4, c = 5$, and $n = 2$ into $(b^2)^n = (bc)^n - (ac)^n + (a^2)^n$ and $(b^3)^n = (b^2c)^n - (abc)^n + (a^2c)^n - (a^3)^n$, respectively, yields the following two equations: $(4^2)^2 = (4 \cdot 5)^2 - (3 \cdot 5)^2 + (3^2)^2$ and $(4^3)^2 = (4^2 \cdot 5)^2 - (3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5)^2 + (3^2 \cdot 5)^2 - (3^3)^2$. That is, $16^2 = 20^2 - 15^2 + 9^2$ and $64^2 = 80^2 - 60^2 + 45^2 - 27^2$.

REFERENCES

- [1] Briggs, W., Cochran, L., Gillett, B., and Schulz, E., *Calculus. Early Transcendentals: Single Variable*, 3rd edition, Pearson Education, Inc., New York, NY, ISBN 13: 978-0-13-476685-0(2019).
- [2] Edwards, H. M., *Fermat's Last Theorem: A Genetic Introduction To Algebraic Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, New York, NY, ISBN 0-387-90230-9 (1977).